

Constitution of β -Naphthapyrones.

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There has been considerable uncertainty regarding the structures of the coumarins derived from β -naphthol. Kauffmann (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 683), who obtained a naphthapyrone (m.p. 118°) by heating β -naphthol-aldehyde with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, formulated it as 1:2- $\beta\beta$ -naphthapyrone having the constitution (I).

It will be readily seen, however, that since the aldehyde group in β -naphthol-aldehyde may be attached to either position 1 or position 3 in the naphthalene ring, the pyrone derived from it may have the following alternative structure of 1:2- $\beta\alpha$ -naphthapyrone (II).

Kauffmann himself regarded his aldehyde (m.p. 81°) as β -naphthol- β -aldehyde, and hence assigned formula (I) to his pyrone. Gattermann (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 285), on the other hand, in view of the great mobility of the α -hydrogen atom in β -naphthol, formulated the same aldehyde as β -naphthol- α -aldehyde. In the latter case, the pyrone derived from it would obviously have formula (II).

Pechmann and Welsh (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1651) claimed to have prepared, by the usual method of condensation of β -naphthol and malic acid in presence of hot concentrated sulphuric acid, a β -naphthapyrone crystallising in yellow needles (m.p. 141°), different from that described by Kauffmann, but no definite structure seems to

have been assigned to the compound by these authors. Since then, it has been customary in literature to refer to Kauffmann's compound as β -naphthacoumarin and to Pechmann's compound as *iso*- β -naphthacoumarin, without defining clearly the precise nature of their difference.

The aldehyde prepared from β -naphthol in the usual manner is now generally considered to be the 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, but direct proof of such a constitution has been lacking. Recently, however, Boehm and Profft (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1931, **269**, 25, 37) claim to have synthesised the isomeric 2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde (m.p. 99-100°) by the reduction of the acid chloride of 2-naphthol-3-carboxylic acid with palladised barium sulphate, thereby setting at rest all doubts regarding the constitution of the other aldehyde. Boehm and Profft have also succeeded in preparing from the new aldehyde, by the application of Perkin's reaction, another isomeric β -naphthacoumarin (m.p. 164°) which is different from both Kauffmann's and Pechmann's compounds, and which must obviously be the 1:2- $\beta\beta$ -naphthapyrone of structure (I). The formulæ of the two β -naphthacoumarins prepared by Kauffmann (structure II) and by Boehm and Profft (structure I) respectively, having thus been definitely established, there remains no other suitable alternative formula to be ascribed to the compound (m.p. 141°) described by Pechmann and Welsh (*loc. cit.*). Moreover, the melting point recorded for the latter compound is found to be the same as that of α -naphthacoumarin (1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone), and it seemed, therefore, to be very necessary to clear up all doubts or confusion existing in the matter by a careful repetition of Pechmann and Welsh's work. The condensation of β -naphthol and malic acid has now been carried out several times with all necessary precautions; the results, which are the same in all cases, are found to be very different from those recorded by previous workers. An orange yellow substance with a beautiful green metallic reflex and of a highly colloidal character, not melting even at 320°, was invariably obtained, while the aqueous sulphuric acid solution yielded, on repeated extraction with ether, a small amount of colourless crystals (m.p. 118°) which was identified as Kauffmann's β -naphthacoumarin, both by analysis and by the method of mixed melting points. No trace of the compound (m.p. 141°) mentioned by Pechmann and Welsh (*loc. cit.*) was ever obtained. The orange solid, which is soluble to some extent in water, appears to have an acidic character as it dissolves in cold alkalis and even in

alkali carbonates to form perfectly colourless solutions. Indeed, the change from deep orange to colourless is so sharp and marked that the substance ought to serve as an excellent indicator for alkalis. Acids reprecipitate the orange solid in a finely divided, almost colloidal condition. This interesting body has so far been obtained in only very poor yields, and a fuller account of its composition and properties has to be deferred till a sufficient quantity has been accumulated.

The problem of the constitution of the methyl- β -naphthacoumarin obtained from β -naphthol and ethyl acetoacetate (Bacovescu, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1280) has also not been satisfactorily solved. Two alternative structures, corresponding to (I) or (II), are also possible in this case, according as the carbon atom in the naphthalene nucleus taking part in this condensation is in 1 or 3 positions, thus:—

Attempts were made (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1615) to arrive at a choice between these two constitutions by oxidising the 4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone to the corresponding 2:3-(or 1:1)-naphthol-carboxylic acid, but they have hitherto been unsuccessful. The structure (IV) has however been advocated for this coumarin, although no direct proof of this constitution is available, mainly on the following grounds:

(a) The condensations of phenols with malic acid, and with ethyl acetoacetate, in presence of sulphuric acid, have always been found to proceed on the same lines, the unsubstituted coumarins and the corresponding 4-methyl substituted coumarins being respectively obtained by the two reactions.

(b) Since it is now definitely proved that the product of condensation of β -naphthol and malic acid is identical with the coumarin obtained by Kauffmann from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, and has, therefore, structure (II), it may reasonably be inferred that the methyl-naphthacoumarin prepared from β -naphthol and ethyl acetoacetate has also a similar, *i.e.*, β_a -structure (IV).

(c) An additional and important reason for giving preference to structure (IV) lay in the observation (Dey, *loc. cit.*, 1616) that the ethyl ester of the naphthacoumarin-4-acetic acid prepared from β -naphthol and ethylacetone dicarboxylate, behave differently from the other coumarin-4-acetic acid ethyl esters and also from the isomeric α -naphthacoumarin-4-acetic acid ethyl ester prepared from α -naphthol and ethylacetone dicarboxylate, the latter being known to have structures akin to (III). On warming the ester with concentrated sulphuric acid, it lost the elements of a molecule of alcohol and formed a compound of the formula $C_{15}H_8O_3$. Since this reaction is exceptional, the other coumarin-4-acetic acids remaining unchanged under these conditions, it has been interpreted as evidence in favour of structure (IV) for β -naphthacoumarin-4-acetic acid, and therefore for 4-methyl- β -naphthacoumarin, the latter being obtained quantitatively from the former by heating above its melting point. The compound, $C_{15}H_8O_3$ designated 5-hydroxy-2-keto-peri-peri-naphthindenofuran, is supposed to be formed in the following manner :—

If this interpretation be accepted it would undoubtedly constitute an important evidence in favour of structures (IV) and (V) for methyl- β -naphthacoumarin and β -naphthacoumarin-4-acetic acid respectively. It must nevertheless be recognised that the arguments which have so far been adduced seem to furnish only indirect proofs, and fresh and more direct evidence in support of the proposed constitutions would be most welcome. This has now been obtained in connection with the study of coumarin-3-acetic acids which has been recently started in this laboratory. β -Naphthol is found to condense with ethylformyl succinate in presence of sulphuric acid in the normal manner giving rise to a coumarin-3-acetic acid, m.p. 264° , (methyl ester, m.p. 149°) (Dey and Sankaranarayanan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 827). The same acid has now been synthesised from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde by heating with sodium succinate and succinic anhydride, thereby fully revealing its constitution as 1:2- β a-

naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid. The following scheme explains the reactions involved.

This observation has thus proved to be of great interest and value on account of the light it throws on the constitution of the coumarins arising from β -naphthol. It indicates very clearly that it is the hydrogen atom in 1 and not that in the 3 position of β -naphthol, which participates in the reaction with β -ketonic esters under the conditions of Pechmann's condensation, and as a consequence, confirms the structures previously assigned to 4-methyl- β -naphthacoumarin (m.p. 179°) and β -naphthacoumarin-4-acetic acid (m. p. 191°).

Considerable amounts of the dicoumarin, 3:3-di-1:2- β -naphthapyrone, were also formed in the reaction between β -naphthol-aldehyde and sodium succinate, according to the following equation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of β -naphthol and malic acid.—A mixture of β -naphthol (14.4 g.) and malic acid (12.5 g.) was heated on wire gauze with concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c. c.). In the initial stages of heating, the liquid mixture, for some unexplained reason, completely solidified. It liquefied again on continuing the heating, and after a short time, began to evolve carbon monoxide. As soon as the mixture commenced frothing vigorously, the burner was removed and the reaction allowed to complete of itself. The cold dark red melt was mixed with cracked ice (500 g.) and allowed to stand for 4 hours. The main bulk of the deeply coloured solution was decanted from the very fine solid which had settled to the bottom, and the latter separated from the small amount of mother-liquor by centrifuging, the fineness of the particles making filtration almost impossible. The solid was washed by stirring with small volume of water, again centrifuged, dried and powdered. A bright orange yellow crystalline powder with a splendid metallic sheen was thus obtained, weighing approximately 0.6 g. It showed no signs of melting even when heated to 320°. The substance hardly dissolved in alcohol, benzene, etc., and could not therefore be crystallised from these solvents. When triturated with excess of water it went into an opalescent, colloidal solution, having a deep orange colour, which became instantly clear and colourless on adding a few drops of dilute alkali or alkali carbonate solutions.

The filtrate from the above was extracted four times with ether, the green fluorescent ether extract evaporated to dryness, and the brownish solid residue rubbed for a few minutes with 2 p. c. caustic soda, and filtered. It was finally crystallised twice from 50 p. c. alcohol in pale yellow needles (m.p. 118°); yield, nearly 1 g. There was no depression of its melting point when mixed with a specimen of the β -naphthacoumarin (m.p. 118°) prepared by Kauffman's method. The identity of the substance with Kauffmann's coumarin was further confirmed by converting it into the *trans*-o-coumaric acid by heating with sodium sulphite and alkali according to the method of Dey and Row (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 554). Both of them yielded the same acid, m.p. 165° (decomp.).

Action of sodium succinate and succinic anhydride on 2-naphthol-1-aldehyde: Formation of 1:2- β -naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid, and 3:3-di-1:2- β -naphthapyrone.— β -Naphthol-aldehyde (7g.) and sodium

succinate dried at 140° for 3 hours (7 g.) are intimately mixed with freshly made succinic anhydride (14 g.) and heated under air reflux on an oil-bath at 180° for 5 hours. On cooling, the hard mass was broken up and left in contact with a solution of sodium carbonate (17g. in 50 c.c.) for 12 hours. The reddish solution was filtered from the insoluble residue, the filtrate carefully acidified with HCl, and the brown coloured precipitate collected, washed and dried. It melted at $250-55^\circ$, and weighed 3.8 g. It was insoluble in water and dissolved very sparingly in alcohol but more readily in hot glacial acetic acid. A single crystallisation from the latter solvent raised the melting point to 264° , not depressed by admixture with the product obtained from β -naphthol and ethylformyl succinate (Dey and Sankaranarayanan, *loc. cit.*). (Found: M. W., (by titration with $N/10$ alkali), 251. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires M.W., 254).

The *methyl ester*, prepared in the usual manner, melted at 149° , and was identified with the methyl ester of the corresponding acid obtained from ethylformyl succinate.

The insoluble residue which had a dark yellow colour was left in contact with N -alkali (50 c.c.) for 2 hours, filtered, and the residue thoroughly washed with cold water. The clear filtrate, on acidification, deposited a small quantity of an impure tar which could not be investigated further. The yellow residue still melted indefinitely ($270-90^\circ$); it was purified by boiling for 5 minutes with $N/2$ -alkali (50 c.c.), and quickly filtering the hot solution. Two such washings raised the melting point of the crude product to 330° , yield 1.9 g. (approx.). It was practically insoluble in alcohol, benzene, acetic acid and the other common organic solvents; it dissolved sparingly in boiling pyridine and more readily in hot nitrobenzene, and was finally crystallised from the latter solvent and washed with hot alcohol. Beautiful golden yellow needles, m.p. 345° , yield 1.4 g. (Found: C, 79.27; H, 3.79. $C_{26}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 80.0 H, 3.59 per cent.).

